

JGR: Oceans

Supporting Information for

Tracing Ocean Circulation and Mixing from the Arctic to the Subpolar North Atlantic Using the ^{129}I – ^{236}U Dual Tracer

Duncan Dale¹, Marcus Christl², Christof Vockenhuber², Andreas Macrander³, Sólveig Ólafsdóttir³, Rob Middag^{4,5} and Núria Casacuberta^{1,2}

Contents of this file

Figure S1

Table S1

Additional Supporting Information (Files uploaded separately)

Captions for Tables S2 to S3

Introduction

- Supporting information on the input functions of ^{129}I and ^{236}U to the Arctic Ocean, glossary of water masses and currents, key to tracer seawater categories used in this study, and full data and metadata of all samples measured or otherwise used in this study.

Figure S1. Surface and Atlantic layer input functions of ^{129}I and ^{236}U to the Arctic Ocean (Casacuberta et al. 2018)

AAW	Arctic Atlantic Water
AIW	Arctic Intermediate Water
ArcW	Arctic-origin Water
AW	Atlantic Water
DAAW	Dense Arctic Atlantic Water
DSOW	Denmark Strait Overflow Water
IFSJ	Iceland-Faroe Slope Jet
IrSPMW	Irminger Sea Subpolar Mode Water
ISAIW	Iceland Sea Arctic Intermediate Water
ISDW	Iceland Sea Deep Water
ISOW	Iceland Scotland Overflow Water
IW	Irminger Water
LSW	Labrador Sea Water
MEIW	Modified East Icelandic Water
(MN)AW	(Modified North) Atlantic Water
NADW	North Atlantic Deep Water
NEADW_u	Northeast Atlantic Deep Water (upper)
NIIC	North Iceland Irminger Current
NIJ	North Iceland Jet
NSAIW	Norwegian Sea Arctic Intermediate Water
NSDW	Norwegian Sea Deep Water
PSW	Polar Surface Water
PSW_w	Warm Polar Surface Water
RAW	Recirculating Atlantic Water
RetAW	Return Atlantic Water
SAIW4	Subarctic Intermediate Water 4 °C
SAIW6	Subarctic Intermediate Water 6 °C
SPMW7	Subpolar Mode Water 7 °C
SPMW8	Subpolar Mode Water 8 °C
uPDW	upper Polar Deep Water

Table S1. Glossary of Water Masses / Currents

Table S2. Key to tracer seawater categories used in this study and endmember tracer concentrations

Table S3. Metadata and radionuclide concentrations for all samples used in this study